

A coding schema for annotation of givenness in spontaneous conversations: Discourse and situational status

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Motivation

Givenness plays a central role in studies of information structure. It is a factor that explains language users' behaviour, including the use of case marking, word order and the choice of referential expressions. However, it is difficult to study its effects on language structure and use because givenness has been defined in many ways (cf. Chafe 1976, 1994; Prince 1981; Siewierska 1988; Dipper et al. 2007). For example, a referent can be considered given because it has been mentioned in discourse (Halliday 1967: 205), or because it is at the foreground of the language user's consciousness (Chafe 1976), or because it belongs to shared knowledge and therefore can be easily inferred (Prince 1981). This makes studying the effects of givenness very challenging.

The coding schema described below aims to help linguists to annotate givenness in naturalistic data. It was created for annotation of the core grammatical roles (A and P) in transcripts of spontaneous spoken conversations in German, Russian and Tagalog, but it can be adjusted to other text types, modalities and expressions. The schema was modified until acceptable interrater agreement scores were achieved.

The main distinguishing characteristic of this coding schema is that givenness is represented by two variables. One of them describes the status of the referent in discourse, based on what has been said during the interaction. The other variable reflects how accessible a referent is based on the extralinguistic situation. It is possible to combine these two variables, if necessary. In addition, Prince's distinction between familiar and unfamiliar referents crosscuts the low-accessibility categories (New and Absent) in both variables.

Description of the variables and annotation algorithm

Variable 1. Discourse_Status

The values are coded based on the text only, as represented in the transcripts.

Table 1. Overview of all values of *Discourse_Status*.

Label	Meaning
Non-referential	The expression is not referential.
Mentioned_close	The referent is mentioned in the current or previous intonation unit.
Mentioned_far	The referent is mentioned further above than the previous intonation unit.
Mentioned	The referent is mentioned, but you are unsure how close.
Inferable_close	The referent is inferable from a referent mentioned in the current or previous intonation unit.

Inferable_far	The referent is inferable from a referent mentioned further above than the previous intonation unit.
Inferable	The referent is inferable, but you are not sure how close the second referent is.
New_familiar	The referent is neither mentioned, nor inferable, but the speaker assumes that it is in shared knowledge.
New_unfamiliar	The referent is neither mentioned, nor inferable, and not in shared knowledge.
New	The referent is neither mentioned nor inferable, but you are unsure if it is part of shared knowledge.
Unclear	When you really cannot decide.

Annotation algorithm

Question 1: Is the expression referential (can be referred to by an anaphoric pronoun, is not expressed by a question word, negative pronoun, universal pronoun, e.g., German pronoun *man*, English *they*)? Note that idiomatic expressions can also include non-referential nominal expressions. An example is *Recht haben* in German, because one cannot refer to *Recht* later anaphorically. Note also that relativizers (e.g., The book **that** I read) are referential and their previous mention is the head noun or pronoun (in this example, *the book*).

Yes: go to Question 2.

No: code “Non-referential”

Question 2: Has the referent been mentioned in the same conversation within the previous 50 **turns** already? If a text contains long breaks, the fragments before and after a break are considered different conversations.

Notes:

- terms of address count also as mentions, e.g., *Ann* in *Ann*, *do you like this coding schema?*
- the previous mention can be a **pronominal or even an alone-standing finite verb form**, if it unambiguously expresses the subject. For instance, the 1SG present forms in Russian refer to the speaker (e.g., *dumaju...* think.IMPF.PRS-1SG).
- for relativizers in relative clauses, the previous mention is the head noun or pronoun, e.g., *the book* in *The book that I read*.
- If a turn is disrupted by a short expression (e.g., backchanneling uh-uh or something else), it is still considered as one turn.
- If there is a long pause between two contributions by the same speaker, they are counted as two turns.

Yes: **Question 2a:** Is the most recent mention in the current intonation unit or in the immediately preceding one?

Example: Sue went to the garden || **It** was full of exotic flowers.

Yes: code “Mentioned_close”.

No: code “Mentioned_far”.

Unsure: code “Mentioned”.

No: go to Question 3.

Question 3: Is the referent inferable from a referent mentioned previously (using the same limitations as in Question 2), or can it be determined from a verb form in a pro-drop structure (e.g., Try it, **you**’ll like it)?

Examples:

- a. I bought a bicycle || **The saddle** is very comfortable (part-whole relationship)
- b. Sue went to the garden || **The flowers** were beautiful (part-whole relationship)
- c. I went to work by bus || **The driver** was rude.
- d. Sue bought eggs || **One of the eggs** was bad (subset relationship)
- e. I’ve just made coffee. Would you like some? || I hate **coffee**! (superset relationship)
- f. The children were swimming in the lake || **The family** went to this place every summer (superset relationship)
- g. The garden was full of exotic flowers || **Their scent** was very intensive (entity-attribute relationship)
- h. I’m leaving with Sue tomorrow || **We** want to party in Las Vegas (aggregate relationship)
- i. I like tea || But my partner prefers **coffee** (members of the same set of hyponyms).

Yes: **Question 3a:** is the second referent (or the omitted argument of the verb) in the current or immediately preceding intonation unit?

Yes: code “Inferable_close”.

No: code “Inferable_far”.

Unsure: code “Inferable”.

No: go to Question 4.

Question 4: Is the referent assumed by the speaker to be part of shared knowledge (e.g., Aunt Mary, Granny Tanya, Buratino/Pinocchio, Winnie-the-Pooh, the neighbours)?

Examples:

- a. Do you like this cake? **Granny Tanya** made it for us.
- b. Many people believe that **Bill Gates** is evil.

Yes: code “New_familiar”.

No: code “New_unfamiliar”.

Unsure: code “New”.

Variable 2. Situation_Status

The values are coded on the basis of what we think the extralinguistic situation or context is for the interlocutors, as far as we can infer this information from the text and metadata. By extralinguistic situation/context discussed below we mean **information perceptually accessible to both (or all, if there are more) interlocutors when the utterance is produced**. This information can come from all types of perception: visual, auditory (e.g., someone's knocking at the door), haptic/tactile (related to touch), olfactory (e.g., a strange smell) or related to taste.

Table 2. Overview of all values of *Situation_Status*.

Label	Meaning
Nonreferential	The expression is not referential.
Present_salient	The referent is present in the assumed extralinguistic context and salient.
Present_nonsalient	The referent is present in the assumed extralinguistic context and not salient.
Present	The referent is present in the assumed extralinguistic context, but you are not sure if it is salient or not.
Inferable_salient	The referent is inferable from a salient referent present in the assumed extralinguistic context.
Inferable_nonsalient	The referent is inferable from a non-salient referent present in the assumed extralinguistic context.
Inferable	The referent is inferable from a referent present in the assumed extralinguistic context, but you are not sure if the latter is inferable or not.
Absent_familiar	The referent is neither present, nor inferable, but the speaker assumes that it is part of shared knowledge.
Absent_unfamiliar	The referent is neither present, nor inferable, and not part of shared knowledge.
Absent	The referent is neither present, nor inferable, but you are not sure if it is part of shared knowledge.
Unclear	When you really cannot decide.

Annotation algorithm

Question 1: Is the expression referential (can be referred to by an anaphoric pronoun, is not expressed by a question word, negative pronoun, universal pronoun)?

Yes: go to Question 2.

No: code “Non-referential”

Question 2: Is the referent present in the assumed extralinguistic context available for both interlocutors to our best judgement? See the definition of extralinguistic context above.

Yes: **Question 2a:** Is the referent one of the speech act participants (or both)?

Example: Do **you** like ice-cream?

Yes: code “Present_salient”

No: **Question 2b:** Is the referent in the focus of both interlocutors’ attention?

Example: Look at my new toy (showing a toy of Winnie-the-Pooh) **Winnie-the-Pooh** is hungry!

Yes: code “Present_salient”

No: code “Present_nonsalient”

Unsure: code “Present”

No: go to Question 3.

Question 3: Is the referent inferable from a referent present in the extralinguistic context? Note: see examples of inferability in *Discourse_Status*.

Yes: **Question 3a:** Is the second referent one of the speech act participants (or both)?

Example: **My mother** is visiting me tomorrow.

Yes: code “Inferable_salient”

No: **Question 3b:** Is the second referent in the focus of the interlocutors’ attention?

Example: Look at my new toy! (showing a toy of Winnie-the-Pooh) And Jack bought **Piglet!**

Yes: code “Inferable_salient”

No: code “Inferable_nonsalient”

Unsure: code “Inferable”

No: go to Question 4.

Question 4: Is the referent assumed by the speaker to be part of shared knowledge (e.g., aunt Mary, Granny Tanya, Buratino/Pinocchio, Winnie-the-Pooh, the neighbours) at this point of communication? See examples in *Discourse_status*. Note: we also count as familiar if a referent has been mentioned, e.g. I’ve read an interesting book about linguistics. **It** won a prestigious prize [Absent_familiar]

Yes: code “Absent_familiar”

No: code “Absent_unfamiliar”

Unsure: code “Absent”

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